

Journalism and Generative AI: Data, Deals and Disruption in the News Media

*Findings from an expert workshop exploring the issues
arising from AI companies' use of news as data for training
and grounding AI systems*

• • • Executive Summary

The rapid development and productisation of generative AI, often using news as data for training and grounding models, has prompted the news industry to respond – some with lawsuits, others with data licensing agreements, but all with renewed attention to their position in a shifting media ecosystem. As the UK government considers expanding the text and data mining exception in copyright law and promotes AI adoption and industry in the newly released AI Opportunities Action Plan¹, there is a need to understand how changes wrought by generative AI are impacting the news media specifically.

In November 2024, **BRAID (Bridging Responsible AI Divides)** and the **Ada Lovelace Institute** organised an expert workshop, under Chatham House rules, to explore the state of play in news publishing, including pressing challenges, current responses, and emerging safeguards and solutions. We heard from major news publishers, AI and natural language processing experts, lawyers and legal scholars, and copyright experts.

The workshop sought to answer three core questions:

1. What is the state of play in news publishing regarding news as data for AI models?
2. What concerns does this situation raise for news publishers and society?
3. What solutions/safeguards could support news publishers and the sustainable provision of a plurality of public interest news?

News publishers' top concerns relate to a) copyright infringement and violation of intellectual property laws by AI companies alongside b) direct competition from their development of new products like generative search and news summaries, which may profit from unlicensed use of news organisations' work without fair compensation or attribution and/or have poor standards and product performance that put their reputations at risk. The lack of transparency from AI companies and their growing position as intermediaries between news publishers and their audiences make disputing their actions and seeking recourse a significant challenge that without mitigation, risks harming the news ecosystem and the publics it serves.

To date, the safeguards available to news publishers are not sufficient to address these concerns. To support a resilient and pluralistic news industry and workforce, stronger protections around intellectual property, greater transparency about what news content is used in training and grounding AI models, improved routes for contestability and redress, and fairer models for compensation will be needed.

Notably, many concerns relate to the live inference processes whereby new AI products like generative search or news summaries draw from and attribute news organisations' journalism in problematic ways. However, most existing safeguards and solutions pertain to the pre-training of AI models at the upstream layers of the supply chain (i.e. in foundation

1 <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/ai-opportunities-action-plan/ai-opportunities-action-plan>

models), leaving publishers with little recourse to rectify potentially damaging impacts further downstream. Increased attention to understanding and addressing issues introduced by midstream and downstream layers of the AI supply chain, for instance during inference and retrieval augmented generation (RAG), and the interdependencies between these layers will be needed.

The following report captures key findings drawn from participants' contributions, supplemented with insights from secondary research.

● ● ● Context

The rapid development and commercialisation of generative AI, including language, image, audio and video models, has raised concerns about undesirable impacts on the news industry and wider information ecosystem. Core to these concerns are claims of copyright infringement for use of news content to train AI models without a license and the wider implications for intellectual property (IP) rights. Alongside others across the creative industries, many news organisations are suing AI companies, but the response in the industry has been fragmented. While some are suing², others are signing deals that license their data troves³, and still others are doing both. For example, the Wall Street Journal and New York Post have filed a copyright and trademark infringement lawsuit against AI start-up Perplexity, while simultaneously, parent firm News Corp has signed a deal with OpenAI. The New York Times was in negotiations with OpenAI and Microsoft, but then abruptly pulled out to launch one of the most high-profile suits to date, seeking damages, restitution and costs as well as the destruction of LLMs trained on its content. However, lawsuits in this space are not just about data. Dow Jones and the New York Post also have a lawsuit against Perplexity arguing that hallucinations attributed to news outlets are illegal.⁴ Moreover, striking deals does not appear to shield publishers from the risk of their content being misattributed or misrepresented⁵ in new products like generative search (e.g. Google's AI Overviews, Perplexity, SearchGPT) and news summaries (e.g. Apple news alerts)⁶.

Even without data deals, some publishers are allowing AI companies to crawl and scrape news content from their websites under pressure to retain visibility with audiences⁷. Others are blocking crawlers and seeking industry-wide solidarity and collective bargaining power, including many smaller publishers, which are predicted to face disproportionate impacts. In this context, a nascent licensing market is developing with new intermediary organisations being established to facilitate agreements. This is all taking place amid conditions of significant legislative and regulatory uncertainty.

2 <https://www.mishcon.com/generative-ai-intellectual-property-cases-and-policy-tracker>

3 <https://pressgazette.co.uk/platforms/news-publisher-ai-deals-lawsuits-openai-google/>; see also database from the Tow Centre's Pete Brown <https://petebrown.quarto.pub/pnp-ai-partnerships/>

4 <https://www.wired.com/story/dow-jones-new-york-post-sue-perplexity/>

5 https://www.cjr.org/tow_center/how-chatgpt-misrepresents-publisher-content.php

6 Apple suspends error-strewn AI generated news alerts, BBC News: <https://www.bbc.co.uk/news/articles/cq5ggew08eyo>

7 <https://www.theverge.com/24067997/robots-txt-ai-text-file-web-crawlers-spiders>

SPOTLIGHT: Key arguments of major lawsuits

1. **Copyright infringement:** AI companies have scraped news articles and content to train their models without permission, violating existing copyright law.
2. **Breach of terms of use:** The process of scraping news websites violates their terms of use, bypassing access controls and restrictions meant to prevent automated data collection.
3. **Trademark infringement:** Generative AI tools present data gleaned from news sources as their own, misrepresenting themselves as authoritative sources of information and diluting the credibility and value of news brands.
4. **Lack of attribution:** AI tools fail to, or cannot, attribute to sources correctly, misleading their users and undermining news brand value.
5. **Harm to business models:** AI companies' provision of (rephrased) summaries and snippets of news content reduces traffic to news websites, depriving them of ad revenue and/or subscription income.
6. **Lack of compensation:** News publishers invest large sums in their newsrooms and journalists to build credible, reliable, trusted content. By using this content in training or inference, AI companies profit from news publishers' investment without permission or compensation.

SPOTLIGHT: Key characteristics of major deals⁸

Publishers give:

- Rights to news archive for training data (e.g. *Associated Press-OpenAI*)
- Real-time access to news
e.g. paywalled material to enable new summaries (e.g. *Axel Springer-OpenAI*)
e.g. feed of real-time information for chat apps (e.g. *Associated Press-Google and Agence France-Presse-Mistral*)
- Most are non-exclusive but may contain elements of exclusivity

Publishers get:

- Cash payment
e.g. *News Corp-OpenAI* - \$250+ million over 5 years
e.g. *Axel-Springer-OpenAI* - tens of millions of euros
- (Projected) revenue share
e.g. *Der Spiegel-Perplexity* - publisher earns at least a double-digit percentage of the ad revenue on a per-source basis when content is featured in search results
- Citation and link back to the original source when included in genAI product response (e.g. *Atlantic-OpenAI*)

8 Sources: <https://variety.com/vip-special-reports/generative-ai-content-licensing-special-report-1236157051/>; <https://www.ft.com/content/9200122d-bb4d-4f13-b9db-4991815026b4>

Some deals also include logo and article title displayed (e.g. *Le Monde-OpenAI*)

- Access to technology and/or product expertise (e.g. *AP-OpenAI*), including credits to use paid-for systems
 - e.g. *Perplexity-Der Spiegel* gives access to Perplexity’s Enterprise Pro tier for employees for 1 year + developer tools and its LLMs via API
 - e.g. *Atlantic-OpenAI* gives access to OpenAI technology to develop new AI-powered products for audiences through ‘Atlantic Labs’

There are many unknowns for news organisations in this context. It is not yet clear if new (gen)AI products and services will be a substitute or complement for existing news provision - or ultimately do both. Nor can audience behaviour be reliably predicted. Some publishers reported a “substantial drop in engagement from search” of as much as 5-10% following the UK launch of Google’s AI Overviews⁹ - a feature that provides summary responses to queries written by a language model drawing from live information on the Internet. This adds to large falls in referral traffic to news sites from Facebook (67%) and Twitter (50%) over the last two years¹⁰. However other calculations suggest aggregate traffic from search remains stable¹¹. There is not yet a body of robust empirical work to indicate how significantly news consumption - and crucial click-through rates which impact advertising revenue streams - will be impacted.

Moreover, little is known about how financial recompense in licensing deals is being calculated, or about how news data is being valued. Most contractual details remain confidential and protected by non-disclosure agreements. The few examples of headline figures shared in press releases indicate deals equal to 1% or less of the media company’s revenue¹², suggesting limited direct financial gains and raising questions about whether this amounts to fair recompense¹³. Most deals are also short-term with no guarantee of renewal. However, AI companies continue to need more and more high-quality data, so the market for training data and for grounding¹⁴ models with sources of accurate and timely information will not disappear. How this market develops will however depend heavily on the outcome of pending litigation, legislative and regulatory changes, and technological advancements including towards smaller models and training on synthetic data.

• • • Key concepts to understand

Generative AI (GenAI): A type of AI system that can produce content such as images, videos, audio, and text, e.g. ChatGPT or Stable Diffusion. Most current generative AI systems are built using a technique called deep learning. This uses artificial neural networks comprised of multiple layers of interconnected processing nodes, which “learn” how to generate new instances of the type of data they were trained on in response to prompts. Most depend on extensive web-sourced training datasets collected using web crawling and scraping¹⁵.

9 <https://uk.themedialeader.com/publishers-say-googles-ai-overviews-have-reduced-traffic-potential/>

10 <https://doi.org/10.60625/risj-vte1-x706>

11 <https://doi.org/10.60625/risj-vte1-x706>

12 <https://www.niemanlab.org/2024/12/publishers-find-the-ai-era-not-all-that-lucrative/>

13 <https://reutersinstitute.politics.ox.ac.uk/news/we-need-clarity-about-deals-between-ai-companies-and-news-publishers-heres-why>

14 Google description of grounding in search <https://cloud.google.com/vertex-ai/generative-ai/docs/grounding/overview>

15 Bridging the Data Provenance Gap Across Text, Speech and Video. Shayne Longpre et al. <https://arxiv.org/abs/2412.17847>

Web crawling is the process of identifying URLs and traversing the corresponding web pages to find additional links. For instance, large search engines like Google send their robot crawlers (e.g. Googlebot) out into the network to index Internet content.

Web scraping is the process of using an application to extract information from a website, downloading the content for some further use.

Large Language Model (LLM): A type of machine learning model trained on significant amounts of text data that can generate natural language responses to user input and prompts in order to perform a range of text-based tasks such as answering questions, translation, and summarisation.

News publisher data may be used during three main points of generative AI and LLM development and deployment¹⁶.

Pre-training involves feeding AI models large datasets so they learn to recognise patterns or correlations and can then make inferences based on new inputs. For instance, when pre-training LLMs, data is split into tokens - words or parts of words - and statistical correlations are derived and encoded as vectors, which the model uses to iteratively refine its representations of language by adjusting the parameters to fit the training data until it performs well enough in the pre-training task.

Fine-tuning involves further training a pre-trained model on a smaller, targeted dataset to adapt it to suit more specialised use cases and tasks.

Inference and retrieval augmented generation (RAG): Inference is the process that a trained AI model uses to draw conclusions from new data. RAG is a technique that enables generative AI models to retrieve supporting data from information sources (e.g. knowledge bases, APIs, the web) to generate enriched responses to a user's prompt and provide a source citation.

¹⁶ Additional uses include evaluation, verification and validation.

Common issues with generative AI: Hallucinations (also called confabulation), the generation of nonsensical or inaccurate outputs; Biases derived from training data and design that unfairly disadvantage certain groups or individuals; Inaccuracy and fabrication, including false attribution of content to incorrect or non-existent sources; Memorisation and regurgitation of works included in training data without attribution; Generation of libellous or defamatory content; Inherent mutability whereby a model may or may not generate a different response to the same input each time.

Workshop Insights

Though news publishers have been a leading voice in the conversation around copyright and IP and are the largest group of existing licensors¹⁷, not all of them see the strategic benefit of doing deals at this point. They have differing approaches that reflect their audiences, revenue structures, brands and values. Despite these differences, there are a set of core concerns, explained below.

● ● ● News publishers' core concerns

- 1. Copyright infringement and prohibited data extraction:** Like other creators and owners of copyright-protected media content, news publishers have seen automated data extraction of their online content for AI model training and use without permission or remuneration¹⁸. While publishers claim copyright infringement, AI companies continue developing and using models trained on this material unabated, citing fair use, public interest or technical defences. Some AI companies are ignoring robots.txt and other protocols aimed at restricting web crawling and scraping, while new crawlers are released at a rapid rate, making it hard for news publishers to keep up with documentation to block them and placing a burden on those without dedicated teams. Publishers voiced concern that existing web indexing and service agreements which enable crawling to make their news searchable and visible online were being exploited for AI training and product development and their data was being used in ways that are obscured to them.
- 2. Lack of transparency:** The lack of transparency from AI companies about what data has been used to train their models, and the importance and value of different types of data to those models, leaves publishers in the dark. The value of news content appears to vary across the spectrum of data uses (pre-training, fine-tuning, inference) but to what extent is difficult to gauge. For pre-training, some claim the corpus of news in LLM training data is less than 1%, whilst some research and publisher analysis of datasets^{19,20} suggest significantly more. For example, an exploration of an open-source replica of the corpus used to train OpenAI's GPT-2 (OpenWebText) found that mainstream news forms the overwhelming majority of content in the dataset, with the BBC and Guardian websites alone representing 3% of total documents²¹. News publishers query why AI companies are

17 Joint with stock image companies - correct as of December 2024

18 See e.g. https://pressgazette.co.uk/media_law/millions-of-nyt-and-ny-daily-news-stories-taken-by-openai-for-training-data/

19 <https://www.washingtonpost.com/technology/interactive/2023/ai-chatbot-learning/>

20 <https://www.regulations.gov/comment/COLC-2023-0006-8868>

21 <https://arxiv.org/pdf/2201.10474v2>

negotiating contracts with them if there is little value. There is recognition that news can have particular value for fine-tuning models for a subset of specific products and services, including for low-resource and minority languages, but more importantly, during inference when a model uses RAG to answer a query with up-to-date and reliable information – the bread-and-butter of news. High-quality news may also hold value given fears of model collapse if future AI models are trained on AI-made synthetic content, though such predictions have been critiqued for overstating the risk²².

3. **Unfair recompense and opaque deals:** Most news publishers are still receiving no recompense for their data being used in training AI models or during inference. Whilst a growing number of larger, mainly English-language, upmarket players are negotiating or have struck deals, most smaller publishers, be they local or niche market news organisations, do not have a seat at the table. There is also very little transparency about the content of deals, making it difficult for those publishers wishing to strike agreements to calibrate the market value of their data. Only the biggest publishers benefit in this context and there is widespread concern that this exacerbates winner-takes-most dynamics and pressures on the sustainability of a pluralistic news ecosystem. Additionally, handing over archives and access to their news, which is expensive to produce, risks further empowering the very companies that may in turn put them out of business.
4. **Direct competition:** News publishers are concerned that AI companies will become direct competitors by further developing products and services like generative search and summarisation (e.g. Google's AI Overviews, Perplexity's search engine, and future bespoke agents) that compete for audience attention while using publisher data. This cuts into the core 'currency' of news publishers – timely access to accurate and up-to-date information – and they fear it will reduce traffic to their sites and products, in turn shrinking audiences, advertising revenue, and brand recognition²³. They see this as qualitatively different to search arrangements, arguing a shift from a 'shop window' for third-party content to creating a new rival suite of products. Ultimately, they argue, this will make their businesses less viable/unsustainable and undermine their ability to inform the public, as AI companies profit from the work they have funded.
5. **Poor AI product performance and editorial standards:** News publishers contend that standards of inference accuracy, appropriate attribution, provenance transparency, and linking are not sufficient, and that there is no indication that striking deals can effectively deliver on these requirements. AI firms are moving further into territory in which there are established (if not always universally observed) editorial standards with little experience of this area, nor evidence of concerted efforts to uphold those standards. They have released consumer-facing applications that remain unreliable with respect to accuracy, information integrity and balance. It is also very unclear how prominence of sources are/will be weighted or how editorial decisions are/will be managed. This has sparked concerns that prioritising

22 See e.g. <https://theconversation.com/what-is-model-collapse-an-expert-explains-the-rumours-about-an-impending-ai-doom-236415> and <https://www.transformernews.ai/p/synthetic-data-model-collapse-fears>

23 A concern reflected across the industry with 74% of survey respondents in a Reuters Institute report saying they are worried about a potential decline in referral traffic from search engines in 2025 https://reutersinstitute.politics.ox.ac.uk/sites/default/files/2025-01/Trends_and_Predictions_2025.pdf

some sources over another, if politically or commercially motivated, would skew the free flow of information, and lead to political divides or further bias. What happens if an AI developer holds deals with e.g. mainly left- or right-wing news organisations and gives them preferential treatment in responses and citations? How does that impact the average user's exposure to diverse perspectives? What about those without deals – do they become invisible?

6. **Lack of oversight and loss of control:** The inability to monitor how their content is being summarised, cited, and displayed for each user individually and the subsequent inability to prevent or revise errors, inaccuracies, confabulations, missing information or misattribution in generative AI output is a serious concern for news publishers individually, and collectively for the industry. Unlike broadcasting, this user-content interaction happens in closed data environments, on a one-to-one basis, and the output can change every time it is generated. This raises the question of liability for generated content and the risk of undermining brand control in a sector where trust is core to the business.
7. **Harm to news ecosystem and publics:** Ultimately, publishers worry that without mitigations, the cumulative impacts of points 1-6 will be a diminished information ecosystem with fewer reliable sources of accurate information, fewer independent news sources, and less investigative and original journalism, leading to less availability for audiences of trustworthy information. They also saw a risk that audiences will carry over high-level heuristics they have historically used to gauge trustworthiness of news to new generative products - but these will not hold in this new context, leading to misplaced trust and degradation of the estimation of news in the eyes of the public. This situation also brings new inflections to concerns around echo chambers and filter bubbles when individual news consumers engage with chat interfaces and AI agents as an entry point to news that may hyper-personalise to their existing beliefs.

Wider concerns

Additionally, some participants raised concerns about the detrimental impact on the data commons if news publishers license to big tech companies but pull back from enabling the datasets (like Common Crawl) that researchers and smaller developers rely on. It was recognised that many IP and data owners contributing to the common good are facing the same issues (e.g. Wikimedia) without the kind of lobby and leverage available to the news industry. They questioned whether individual journalists (employees, freelancers, self-publishing journalists) were being properly considered and would actually benefit from publishers' licensing arrangements and the new status quo. Others highlighted that addressing issues raised by generative AI are only one part of a bigger puzzle about how to protect independent news sources and create a media environment where people feel there is trustworthy information.

What news publishers want

Overall, the news publishers in our workshop are looking for fair data practices and a pathway to sector sustainability, i.e. the ability to generate sufficient commercial value from their content through viable income streams that will not undermine their future operation. Beyond fair recompense and an end to unlicensed data use, this involves upholding their high-quality editorial standards and receiving proper attribution in AI products and services, ensuring use of their data complements rather than replaces their products, and retaining access to consumer data to understand the audience. These were priorities they wanted to see reflected in data deals with AI companies. However, it should not be assumed that large incumbent publishers, smaller and local publishers, and individual news-workers share the same concerns or prioritisation of those concerns, or follow high-quality editorial standards in similar ways. Smaller independent publishers were not present in the workshop, nor were representatives of individual journalists, and their needs and perspectives have been less well-represented on these topics to date.

● ● ● Challenges publishers face

1. Inadequate means to protect IP rights and restrict unwanted data extraction

1.1. Shortcomings of legal framework: This situation is partly a result of no uniform opt-in/opt-out scheme or standard currently existing in the UK (or EU and US) and the regulation of opt-out mechanisms being unclear. Concern about the UK government's pro-innovation stance and plans to create a broader text and data mining copyright exemption that includes commercial AI training in the near-term – whether transparency and consent conditions are developed in time or not – was voiced by publishers²⁴. The move would bring the UK closer to the EU's copyright framework under the Digital Single Market Copyright Directive 2019/790, but what constitutes legally valid and adequate means to opt out in this framework remains disputed, and the practical viability of machine-readable opt-outs is contested. They believe an opt-out system would be impractical and burdensome as they would not know when their material is being scraped and by which companies and would have to track down the multiple and proliferating uses of their work. Given the existing issues in the EU with making opt-out work, there were concerns that the news industry will find itself still searching for safeguards and solutions in several years' time but from a worse position, and policymakers would have a reduced set of levers to protect the news industry. Some predicted that if opt out does not work well, publishers might find it easier to just take content down, particularly to avoid unlicensed use for RAG in live products, and be reticent to share archives – which would be a bad outcome and could have a chilling effect. There was also recognition that the threat of litigation and AI firms' desire to offset risk may be a driver of current deal-making and moves to widen the exception could reduce their leverage. News publishers held the perception that politicians recognise the value of compute, energy, and

24 Criticisms mirrored by the Creative Rights in AI Coalition (Crac), which includes numerous news publishers including the Guardian, Financial Times, Newsquest and Daily Mail Group, in response to government proposals <https://www.theguardian.com/technology/2024/dec/19/uk-arts-and-media-reject-plan-to-let-ai-firms-use-copyrighted-material>

talent to building AI models and will legislate for these, but they undervalue the importance of news publishers' data in training and grounding models.

1.2. Limitations of existing protocols, standards & tools: There was agreement that existing opt-out mechanisms do not satisfy publisher requirements. The ad-hoc, multiple and messy array of ways to notify AI companies of wishes for material not to be crawled, scraped, or used for AI training, and to block them, were not working as needed. These approaches include:

Robots.txt (Robots Exclusion Protocol), a machine-readable text file that tells crawlers which pages they can and cannot access on a site.

Terms of Service (ToS), alongside other content and copyright policies, enable organisations to delineate more nuanced preferences than robots.txt and specify bans on downstream use cases (e.g. placing restrictions on commercial use, using the data for competing services, or redistribution).

Proprietary tools: AI companies have their own processes and tools for rights holders to opt out, for instance OpenAI has a submission form to opt out each individual work and has said it will develop a Media Manager tool to make this process easier²⁵ but has failed to deliver it so far.

Firewalls and bot management software are ways to actually block crawlers in an attempt to enforce restrictions.

News publishers are using combinations of all these methods – and increasingly so – but they have proven inadequate to dealing with the widespread repurposing of news content for AI²⁶. Criticisms include:

- **Non-binding and not legally enforceable:** Do-not-scrape directives embedded in site directories are non-binding and not legally enforceable, meaning they can be easily circumvented by crawlers used by AI developers. There is evidence many AI companies do not respect ToS requests or robots.txt²⁷ and that this extends beyond text to scraping videos^{28,29} and audio too.
- **Questionable efficacy:** Robots.txt only allows for blocking access to websites, not to individual works and only opts out the specific URL from being scraped for training, not derivatives or plagiarised forms of the copyrighted content. This is also complicated by synthetic training data created by other models, which may have included original works.
- **Binary nature & lack of granular control:** Choice with robots.txt and firewalls is between allowing all content on a website for all purposes or none at all, with no middle-ground or nuance possible. There is no way to communicate detail of what crawlers/scrapers can and can't do, e.g. indexing for search but not for training AI. When permitted to crawl, there is no way to establish and enforce boundaries on the downstream use of data e.g. for fine-tuning or RAG. ToS can express more nuanced preferences but are not machine-readable.

25 https://techcrunch.com/2025/01/01/openai-failed-to-deliver-the-opt-out-tool-it-promised-by-2025/?utm_source=substack&utm_medium=email

26 <https://www.dataprovenance.org/consent-in-crisis-paper>

27 <https://www.dataprovenance.org/consent-in-crisis-paper>

28 <https://www.404media.co/runway-ai-image-generator-training-data-youtube/>

29 <https://www.404media.co/nvidia-sued-for-scraping-youtube-after-404-media-investigation/>

- **Place burden on rights owner:** The cost and effort of identifying all possible uses and users of news content and employing the varied required processes to notify them is on the rights holder, which for individuals and small organisations is too onerous to be viable. The ensuing assumption of tacit permission for works not registered favours AI companies by default. AI company tools are devised to meet their needs and are likely to remain unsatisfactory for publishers given existing unsolved issues with content ID at scale.
 - **Cat-and-mouse game:** Ever-changing developments in, and deployments of, crawlers hinder the ability to update preferences – constantly updating the robots.txt file is resource-intensive and risks missing new/updated crawlers. Vendors of AI blockers claim efficacy, but this is a constant battle as those scraping try to subvert protections without legal repercussions.
 - **No transparency or tracking:** Opting out does not ensure transparency around whether rights have been respected or what has been used by AI companies.
2. **Power & information/knowledge asymmetry:** News publishers – particularly smaller independent providers – already struggle to negotiate a fair commercial relationship with big tech platforms due to their market dominance and publishers’ extensive reliance on them³⁰. This power asymmetry is exacerbated by lack of access to necessary information from AI companies and lack of clarity about the nature of deals they are striking with other news providers.

2.1. Lack of/restricted access to information from AI companies: AI developers have not been required to disclose the data used to train their models, making it difficult for news publishers to know exactly which of their copyrighted works have been used. Tracing an AI output back to specific works used in pretraining and training is very complex (though not always impossible), which makes it incredibly difficult to gauge the value of any corpus of news to the performance of a specific model. This tracing is technically easier to work out for the RAG process but again, this information is not usually made available.

- New rules and proposals around the world may change this situation, including for example, the European Union AI Act’s transparency obligations and in the US state of California, the AB-2013 Generative artificial intelligence: training data transparency. The EU AI Act, which went into effect in 2024, requires developers of large AI models to provide “sufficiently detailed summaries” of the datasets used to train them³¹ - but what constitutes a sufficient level of detail and what can be reasonably enforced (e.g. revealing weights) is still being worked out³².

2.2. Limited leverage & inadequate routes for recourse: Existing routes for news publishers to report complaints about use of their content and to seek redress are ad-hoc and rely on their own efforts monitoring and tracking AI system outputs. Only the largest news organisations have the profile to leverage public attention and/or corporate influence to successfully push AI companies to fix errors or withdraw problematic products or features, as happened with Apple’s erroneous news alerts.

30 Sustainability of local journalism. House of Commons Committee report: <https://publications.parliament.uk/pa/cm5803/cmselect/cmcmds/153/report.html>

31 https://openfuture.eu/wp-content/uploads/2024/09/240919AIAttransparency_template_requirements-blueprint_v.2.0.pdf

32 The General-Purpose AI code of practice will be enforced from Q2 2025: <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/ai-code-practice>

- **Accountability gap:** When errors occur, there is currently no way to hold AI companies to account and it remains unclear where liability lies for incorrect and harmful information generated by AI systems referencing news publishers as the source. Terms of service for most AI firms are constructed specifically to avoid liability, but this has not yet been tested in court in the news context.
- **Smaller publishers have no recourse** because they don't have the funds to sue or the clout to get the AI firms to the table. And the time for collective bargaining may be gone because so many deals have already been done.

● ● ● Emerging solutions, safeguards and interventions

The current landscape for news publishers is one of constantly shifting sands in which there are many open questions and live challenges but few concrete answers or solutions. There is a fragmented array of technical, policy, and industry measures available to publishers – but as described, they are neither comprehensive nor consistently effective. A more structural approach is required. Below, we outline directions where potential solutions might lie and describe proposed safeguards, solutions, and interventions.

1. **Robust legislative opt-in mechanism:** Some news publishers favoured an opt-in system whereby explicit permission would be required. This would from their perspective respect existing copyright law and give the news industry a stronger position to agree licensing terms. There was some hope that opt-out schemes could improve if their characteristics are defined by external bodies, rather than guided by AI companies. Others worried that even a robust opt-in scheme would have limitations, e.g. it could ultimately fail downstream, where news articles were legally or illegally reproduced by other outlets that are not opting out.
 - **Clarity on interpretation of copyright & IP law:** There was agreement that clarity was needed over the scope and interpretation of UK (as well as US and European) copyright and IP law from government and the courts in order to create a stable foundation for news publishers to build on, but recognition that this would likely take a long time and might throw up divergences that in fact muddy the waters.
2. **Improved protocols, standards and tools:** There was consensus that there is an urgent need to make existing internet protocols and standards work or find new ways to ensure IP rights can be asserted, access to content can be controlled, and its use by and within AI systems can be tracked. Comprehensive, transparent, understandable and practicable approaches will be needed. Several avenues were discussed, including strengthening the work of working groups comprising government, academia and industry to make sure any new standard has granular opt-out choices and enables greater control for publishers, e.g. indicating how content may be used by purpose³³. It is not clear what the path would be to a fine-grained standard that could deal with the complexity of, for instance, opting in for training, opting out for RAG, or only for particular parts of RAG etc. but the role of the IETF³⁴ AI Control working group

33 Needham, C & O'Hanlon, P. (2024) Some suggestions to improve robots.txt <https://www.ietf.org/slides/slides-aicontrolws-some-suggestions-to-improve-robotstxt-00.pdf>

34 The Internet Engineering Task Force is the leading standards development organisation for the Internet <https://www.ietf.org/about/introduction/>

and the work of its committee, the Internet Architecture Board (IAB)³⁵ was highlighted as important for making progress. Potential improvements include:

- **Updating robots.txt and/or creating new machine-readable files** to standardise how preferences are signalled to AI companies, including during inference have been proposed, e.g. TDMRep³⁶, /llms.txt³⁷, ai.txt³⁸, trust.txt³⁹. However, the field is fragmented and faces the same issues as robots.txt in that publishers would need to know which crawlers exist and constantly update files. This also raises new questions around how specific a machine-readable opt-out needs to be.
- **Do Not Train' Registries** (e.g. Spawning.AI's Have I Been Trained register) are another mode of notification to AI firms not to use data for AI training – limitations include that they don't work at scale, e.g. for a whole catalogue/library/archive of work, only for individual works or websites, and they require AI companies to voluntarily sign up.
- **Developing standards for embedded content metadata** to incorporate permissions and prohibitions into data fields. Examples of this type of approach are the IPTC updated standard (version 2023.1) for images⁴⁰, C2PA⁴¹, or "noai" and "noimageai" HTML meta tags⁴².
- **API-managed access** which can tailor the information accessible to AI companies so they aren't directly scraping full news text but accessing what the publisher wants to share via a secondary API - but AI companies prefer and are pushing for block relief so they can scrape.

The enduring problem with all these approaches is that they are not enforceable. They require transparency from AI firms and other 'vehicles' are needed to make them meaningful. They require effective accessibility and adoption, compliance, and dispute resolution mechanisms.

3. Transparency obligations on AI companies: The need for mandatory requirements on AI companies to disclose training data so news publishers can know when AI systems are using their content for training – both past and future – was considered fundamental, alongside transparency about any further use during inference and RAG for output generation. This was viewed as a necessary starting point, rather than an answer to news publishers' problems.

- **New legal routes** were seen as promising (primarily EU AI Act – transparency template, but also e.g. California AB-2013 Generative artificial intelligence: training data transparency) but the extent of news media involvement in shaping policy was seen as limited and it was suggested their representatives should be more involved in such concrete policymaking discussions. For instance, the EU AI Office is looking for input on standards for the AI Act transparency templates, obliged to be developed and published over the first 12 months of it coming into force. It was noted that no legislation to date

35 See <https://www.ietf.org/blog/impressions-ai-control-workshop/> and associated paper submissions <https://datatracker.ietf.org/group/aicontrolws/materials/>

36 <https://www.w3.org/community/reports/tdmrep/CG-FINAL-tdmrep-20240510/>

37 See <https://llmstxt.org/>

38 <https://spawning.substack.com/p/aitxt-a-new-way-for-websites-to-set>

39 <https://journallist.net/new-tool-to-deal-with-ai>

40 <https://iptc.org/std/photometadata/specification/IPTC-PhotoMetadata-2023.1.html#data-mining>

41 https://c2pa.org/specifications/specifications/1.4/specs/C2PA_Specification.html

42 <https://www.deviantart.com/team/journal/UPDATE-All-Deviations-Are-Opted-Out-of-AI-Datasets-934500371>

in the UK comes close to meaningfully touching on transparency mandates⁴³ and is a gap that needs to be filled. The need for global co-ordination was emphasised for stitching together different regulatory approaches so that no matter where scraping is being done, a consistent approach is taken.

- New mandates would not solve the issue of data already scraped. Questions were also raised around the difficulty of retroactive application of transparency for AI companies, since once a model has been trained, much of the information needed for transparency will have been lost if it was not maintained, which is often the case. Requirements that enter into force in a few years' time allow AI companies to start properly tracking and retaining information - but models change every two years or so, meaning data in current models will not be relevant. The option of grandfathering (when an old rule continues to apply to some existing situations while a new rule will apply to future cases) was suggested.
 - **Transparency standards:** Efforts are ongoing to develop granular transparency standards through Internet Engineering Task Force (IETF) working groups, including tools for tracking and monitoring, though the non-binding nature of these measures limits their impact.
 - **Industry initiatives** like Fairly Trained, a non-profit organisation for voluntary certification of AI models that are trained without unlicensed copyrighted works, provide an opportunity for AI companies to prove they meet these standards and be recognised as an alternative to the dominant paradigm, providing (news) organisations with a choice to work with models meeting their expectations and matching their values. Others market tools to provide analytics about which web pages are being accessed by AI bots and how often (e.g. Tollbit), which can inform pricing decisions in negotiations, and tools to gauge use of copyrighted text (e.g. Patronus AI's CopyrightCatcher).
4. **Penalties for breaches:** Agreed forms of post-hoc rectification of infringement are needed alongside other penalties such as financial recompense. Penalties for errors in news summaries and responses to search or chatbot queries should also be considered. This raises the question of how to assess and provide proof of breaches and the need for standardised tracing and tracking methods, including industry benchmarks for error rates in LLMs and associated downstream products.
- **Model deletion, algorithmic disgorgement, machine unlearning & data pruning:** Approaches to either destroying a model or modifying it to no longer include specific data, are in their early days of research and it remains unclear whether they could work. While the validity of these approaches is debated in research circles, others view them as whitewashing by AI companies. The success of these methods also depends on AI firms agreeing to them in cases of court-proven copyright infringement.
 - Algorithmic disgorgement has been used in the US for fundamental rights violations like proven discrimination (and coupled with a ban on creating similar systems in future⁴⁴)

43 N.b. Amendments approved by the House of Lords to the Data (Use and Access) Bill in January 2025 address this issue.

44 e.g. the US Federal Trade Commission case against Rite Aid <https://www.ftc.gov/news-events/news/press-releases/2023/12/rite-aid-banned-using-ai-facial-recognition-after-ftc-says-retailer-deployed-technology-without>

but there would likely be a higher barrier to getting it applied as a remedy for copyright infringement.

- Machine unlearning is an exciting field for researchers but not mature enough to be meaningfully incorporated into law and policy discussions and transparency is a requirement for this to work and that isn't yet in place.
- There have been promising experimental solutions with automatic network monitoring and "data poisoning"⁴⁵ (when an AI model's training data is intentionally tampered with, affecting outputs) as well as malware⁴⁶.

5. **Collective action:** Strengthened intra-industry co-operation and co-ordination was recommended to build on what was perceived as a rare degree of consensus and good will amongst journalistic organisations, and a notable amount of wider UK media cross-collaboration. It was acknowledged that working alone risks missing gains from banding together - particularly in countering disproportionate impacts on smaller and less well-established news publishers – and it would be better for news publishers to be able to act more in concert.
- However, competitors usually would not share commercially sensitive information in case viewed as anticompetitive behaviour/acting as a cartel by the Competition and Markets Authority (CMA). This raised the question of whether news publishers could seek temporary dispensation from certain elements of competition law so that they can bargain collectively, encouraging fairer terms for large and small publishers as well as giving the industry more leverage at the bargaining table. A more expansive approach would be to change the legal framework to require negotiations, as happened in Australia with the bargaining code.
 - **Collective bargaining:** Some participants saw collective bargaining as a good idea in principle but stated that it only works when there is no deviation from a shared position, which has already been the case and follows a trend in the news media which tends to see a split even between the big players, so this is realistically unlikely to work. Others felt collective bargaining was not desirable at all and preferred bilateral deals bolstered by other forms of collective action like codes of practice and standards based on shared foundations of the need for explicit consent from publishers for how their content is used.
 - With regard to ensuring genAI systems meet their needs, it was suggested that pooling data to build and fine-tune new models could be an option, though some doubted the utility of this when so many models are already available.
6. **Recognised valuation and evaluation methodologies:** There is a need to establish widely recognised and agreed methodologies for valuation to inform fair compensation as well as agreed benchmarks and standards to evaluate model performance against news publishers' requirements. This relies to some degree on the increased levels of transparency discussed above and may be facilitated by an independent body, e.g. a non-profit.

45 e.g. Nightshade <https://nightshade.cs.uchicago.edu/whatis.html>

46 e.g. "tarpitching" which traps AI crawlers in a maze of static files with no exit links, where they can be fed gibberish data <https://arstechnica.com/tech-policy/2025/01/ai-haters-build-tarpits-to-trap-and-trick-ai-scrapers-that-ignore-robots-txt/>

- **Valuation:** Well-defined and widely accepted principles for calculating value are required, coupled with usable metrics. It was argued that for a more level playing field, news publishers' understanding of the value of different types of data needs to mature and that knowledge needs to be shared across the industry. For instance, news publishers that are having their journalists use genAI in their work are sending the developers much more valuable data than anything they could get by public crawl – but this gets lost in the conversation about value exchange, which is dominated by copyright and IP.
 - **Evaluation:** There are few existing ways to address the issue of poor performance and editorial standards in genAI products (i.e. those issues that don't breach law) because this relies on AI companies voluntarily self-regulating and self-correcting. Suggestions for improving this situation included standardising mechanisms and methodologies to test and audit systems against approved industry benchmarks.
7. **Licensing:** Licensing was seen by news publishers not as a nice to have but as necessity for AI companies to legally acquire the rights to use their copyright-protected content, and their primary available mechanism to set boundaries for downstream use. Licensing has to-date been largely conducted directly via one-to-one negotiations, but establishing an infrastructure for licensing usage rights at scale was seen as a strong option. This mirrors wider industry trends; in one study, 72% of news leaders said they preferred collective deals where the whole industry benefits compared to just 19% who said they preferred going it alone to seek the best deal for one's own company⁴⁷. Collective licensing would rely on formally agreed valuation methodologies and transparency requirements to a greater extent than in the case of bilateral negotiations. Publishers perceived incumbent big tech companies as less willing to pay for data and newer entrants as more willing. They emphasised that licensing needs to enable a recurring revenue stream, not just sporadic or one-off payments.
- **Specific clauses in contracts:** Licensing for specific uses rather than blanket deals will be important to get more control and oversight of how data is being used. This should never be in perpetuity for multiple uses, but for specific use within a set of constraints. It was suggested publishers could learn from the licensing agreements adopted for data archives, which have developed nuanced clauses. They will need to build in the ability to opt out of specific products/features and ways of exiting contracts (e.g. exit clauses) if they feel products are attempting to replace news experience. Deals that involve employee access to genAI systems should consider choices about how user data from news-workers is fed back into model training (e.g. to develop/improve systems to perform tasks they regularly do in their job) – this is valuable data and can be leveraged in negotiations

47 2025 Reuters Institute Trends and Predictions Report, <https://doi.org/10.60625/risj-vte1-x706>

- **Collective licensing and collaborative arrangements:** Marketplaces offering licensing solutions are growing as commercial providers move into the space of connecting AI developers with content sources. From a pragmatic perspective, some publishers perceived a need to reduce friction and wanted the development of some form of platform/market mechanism that works for everybody and at scale. They were watching with interest the growth in commercial intermediaries enabling publishers to monetise content while providing AI developers with data access, including⁴⁸:
 - TollBit, which is giving necessary code and a measurement tool to news organisations for free to measure what is being scraped by whom, then if directed, they change robots.txt to code that blocks LLMs and directs them to a payment mechanism.
 - Prorata.ai, which offers a tool for attribution and monetisation by attributing sources to the output of the language model rather than what is being scraped. They currently take 50% of revenues and are working with e.g. The Financial Times, The Atlantic, Axel Springer, The Guardian.
 - Human Native, which offers a marketplace of ‘clean’ and verified data, helping publishers ready their content for AI models and set a price, taking a 10% fee when sold.
 - ScalePost, which facilitated Perplexity’s revenue-sharing deals with a group of publishers including Der Spiegel and the Texas Tribune
 - Incumbents in web security like Cloudflare were also cited as a promising example of how consent can be managed and other elements of the basic infrastructure of the Internet can be brought into the discussion to try to avoid the fragmentation and bring lots of different actors to the table.
 - Organisations with sub-licensees have also done deals on their behalf, e.g. Shutterstock
- However, this area is nascent and it remains unclear how effective these solutions are. Issues can include ensuring consent since certain deals (e.g. with academic publishers) were being done without awareness or consent of those people who created the data. Journalists are not currently involved at all in discussions and many have found out about their work being licensed by news companies via news reports. The issue of how policies deal with individual content creators was raised and whether new forms of contracts between journalists and news outlets could be a way to enable them to access ongoing revenues. But it was not clear that there is, or indeed consensus that there should be, a way to tell news organisations what to do with any money they receive from collective agreements. Collective management organisations like PRS music licensing were given as examples but it was recognized that the time and resources to set something like this up would be considerable.

48 INMA - Yes, news companies need AI middlemen (here are 3):
<https://www.inma.org/blogs/product-initiative/post.cfm/yes-news-companies-need-ai-middlemen-here-are-3>

8. **Wider knowledge sharing and co-operation:** Participants emphasised that news publishers will need to better engage with a diverse ecosystem of actors.
- Some suggested news organisation and other representatives of stakeholders in journalism should have more pro-active involvement in policymakers' decisions about what kind of conditions are "fair" or "unfair" to their sector to help establish benchmarks to assess fairness of contractual terms. Because news publishers are not sharing information about their deals or discussions with AI companies there has been little scrutiny or open discussion and this means they are operating under the policy radar.
 - More generally, it was agreed improved knowledge sharing and cooperation between technology and media companies was needed to solve issues. News media companies can bring deep editorial expertise and years of experience to the questions AI and technology companies now engaged in media creation and distribution are facing, while AI firms' state-of-the-art knowledge of emerging systems can help news media innovate and exploit new opportunities. This could include participatory arrangements beyond licensing, e.g. to develop internal/consumer-facing tools, which can provide opportunities to agree guardrails that discourage infringing and offensive AI model output and minimise other risks. However, publishers recognised a tension between wanting to improve emerging AI tools and ensuring the sustainability of the news sector. They, and others, questioned whether their engagement could just make AI companies more adept at replacing news organisations and journalists by helping improve their tools and saw a risk this type of collaboration could confer legitimacy on them as a news source. This raises the question of what the broader purpose of engagement is and should be – is it to improve the performance of AI systems, making them more accurate and trustworthy (with no guarantee this will even work)? Or to help news media organisations invest in innovation and use genAI to augment their expertise? It is not clear if anything in current deals or arrangements offers protections to news media against these risks.
 - Permeating the conversation throughout was agreement on the need for global discussion and cooperation. Since the challenges are not territorially restricted, they require global, concerted governance efforts with news organisations working together with policymakers and stakeholders across jurisdictions.
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● ● ● Recommendations for next steps

In this report, we have described the significant challenge news publishers face as generative AI impacts the news landscape. There are no easy answers to the issues raised and it is clear that a combination of interventions will need to be co-developed in relation to each other – in law, policy, technical methods and social arrangements.

Notably, many concerns related to the live inference processes whereby new AI products like generative search or news summaries draw from and attribute news organisations' journalism in problematic ways. However, most existing safeguards and solutions pertain to the pre-training of AI models at the upstream layers of the supply chain (i.e. in base models), leaving publishers with little recourse to rectify potentially damaging impacts further downstream. Increased attention to understanding and addressing issues introduced by midstream and downstream layers of the AI supply chain, for instance during inference and retrieval augmented generation (RAG), and the interdependencies between these layers will be needed.

A number of other lines of enquiry stand out as needing further exploration:

- Should policy be aimed at getting fair terms for publishers or at wider societal good? (How can we have both?)
- What are best practices in genAI data deal-making?
 - What licensing terms should publishers prioritise and how might they differ, e.g. when negotiating with foundational model developers versus smaller, distilled model developers or for training versus fine-tuning versus inference/RAG?
 - What metrics or frameworks are most appropriate to assess the value of news data and ensure fair compensation?
 - Given the growing importance of a) non-English language data and corpora with high degree of language variability and tonal style, and b) quality image, audio and video data, how should their value be calculated?
 - What terms and other mechanisms can ensure models do not falsely attribute or create content that can trigger damage to publishers' reputation and brand?
- What policy strategies can be pursued that reduce harms to the journalistic labour force?
 - Who benefits from deals and how might relationships with journalists and other creatives involved in news publishing be harmed when their work is incorporated in work licensed by their employer?
 - What role should unions, collectives, and other forms of industry organisation play?
- Given the widely publicised concerns about energy and water usage for AI, how might these deals impact news publishers' sustainability commitments and what approaches can help them meet their obligations?
- What are the expectations of audiences in terms of accuracy and consumption of news content mediated by AI tools?

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About the Ada Lovelace Institute

The Ada Lovelace Institute is an independent research institute with a mission to ensure data and AI work for people and society.

It was established by the Nuffield Foundation in early 2018, in collaboration with The Alan Turing Institute, the Royal Society, the British Academy, the Royal Statistical Society, the Wellcome Trust, Luminata, techUK and the Nuffield Council on Bioethics.

It believes that a world where data and AI work for people and society is a world in which the opportunities, benefits and privileges generated by data and AI are justly and equitably distributed and experienced.

About BRAID

BRAID is a UK-wide programme dedicated to integrating Arts and Humanities research more fully into the Responsible AI ecosystem, as well as bridging the divides between academic, industry, policy and regulatory work on responsible AI.

It represents a six-year, £15.9 million investment in enabling responsible AI in the UK, funded by the Arts and Humanities Research Council (AHRC) from 2022 to 2028.

Working in partnership with the Ada Lovelace Institute and BBC, its team brings together expertise in human-computer interaction, moral philosophy, arts, design, law, social sciences, journalism, and AI. BRAID is extended by a network of interdisciplinary researchers and partnering organisations through the delivery of funding calls, community building events, and a series of programmed activities.

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